

EVALUATION OF THE DENSITY FUNCTIONAL THEORY PROPERTIES OF THE NATURAL COMPOUNDS LACTUCIN AND LACTUCOPICRIN

Avaliação das Propriedades da Teoria Funcional da Densidade dos Compostos Naturais Lactucin e Lactucopicrin

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ABSTRACT

Density Functional Theory (DFT) applies electronic density calculations of the molecular system to indicate structural, electronic, and thermodynamic properties since this makes it possible to obtain precise results even when analyzing relatively large molecules, reducing computational costs. This work aimed to investigate the electronic properties of natural sesquiterpene lactone compounds (Lactucin and Lactucopicrin). However, calculations and correlations of electronic and functional properties were used with the aid of the Gaussian 09W software. Given this, the atoms of the B' and C' rings of lactucin proved to be more susceptible to nucleophilic attack, while the atoms of the A' ring proved to be more susceptible to electrophilic attack. In the case of lactucopicrin, the atoms of the A', B', and C' rings proved to be more susceptible to nucleophilic attack, while the hydroxyphenyl group substituted by acetaldehyde proved to be more susceptible to electrophilic attack. Given this, the study establishes an initial panorama of possible substitutions for new metabolite applications.

Key-words: Natural products, DFT, Sesquiterpene lactones.

RESUMO

A Teoria da Densidade Funcional (DFT) aplica cálculos de densidade eletrônica do sistema molecular para indicar as propriedades estruturais, eletrônicas e termodinâmicas, visto que, este viabiliza a obtenção de resultados precisos ainda que sejam analisadas moléculas relativamente grandes, diminuindo o gasto computacional. Dessa forma, o objetivo do trabalho consistiu em investigar as propriedades eletrônicas dos compostos naturais das lactonas sesquiterpênicas (Lactucin e lactucopicrin). Não obstante, foram utilizados cálculos e correlações das propriedades eletrônicas e funcionais como auxílio do software Gaussian 09W. Em vista disso, os átomos dos anéis B' e C' da lactucina revelaram-se mais susceptíveis ao ataque nucleofílico, enquanto os átomos do anel A' se revelaram mais susceptíveis aos ataques eletrofílicos. No caso da lactucopicrin, os átomos dos anéis A', B' e C' revelaram-se mais susceptíveis aos ataques nucleofílicos, enquanto o grupo hidroxifenil substituído por acetaldéido se revelou mais suscetível ao ataque eletrofílico. Diante disso, o estudo estabelece um panorama inicial de possíveis substituições para aplicações de novos metabólitos.

Palavras-chave: Produtos naturais, DFT, Lactonas sesquiterpênicas.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Computational chemistry is made up of chemical theories and computational methods and is widespread in the industry due to the application of techniques that identify natural compounds with bioactivities, helping to reduce time and financial resources in drug development. The prediction of biological activity can be based on physicochemical properties, molecular descriptors, mass ratio, and retention time, among others (FERREIRA *et al.*, 2022).

Among the methods used by computational chemistry to determine compounds is Density Functional Theory (DFT), which applies calculations based on the electronic density of the molecular system to indicate structural, electronic, and thermodynamic properties. The use of DFT makes it possible to obtain precise results even when analyzing relatively large molecules, reducing computational costs (BAIA, 2023; BARROS *et al.*, 2022).

In this context, the natural compounds lactucin and its derivative lactucopicrin are oxygenated tricyclic compounds that belong to the sesquiterpene lactones (STLs) group of compounds, obtained from plant species of the *Asteraceae* family. STLs have antitumor, antiulcer, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties (CANKAR *et al.*, 2022; ERDENETSOGT *et al.*, 2022).

Given this, the aim is to investigate the electronic and energetic properties of the natural compounds lactucin and lactucopicrin, given their dissemination and application in various segments of the chemical-pharmacological industry.

2. METODOLOGY

All the quantum-mechanical calculations using the DFT method were carried out using the Gaussian 09W software (FRISCH, 2009) in the gaseous state, in a vacuum, and with symmetry restrictions. To identify the three-dimensional coordinates that indicate the minimum energy of the ground state, the geometric optimization process of the structures was carried out using Becke's three-parameter hybrid functional (B3) (BECKE, 1992) for exchange and the gradient-corrected correlation functional of Lee, Yang and Parr (LYP) (LEE; YANG; PARR, 1988) and the Pople 6-311++G(d,p) basis set (PAPAJAK *et al.*, 2011). This functional and basis set was chosen because it has excellent performance in the study of organic molecules.

To study the reactivity of atomic centers, we studied the condensed Fukui functions, which describe the electronic density of the frontier orbitals about changes in the total number of electrons. In this way, Fukui functions (FF) make it possible to study the most electrophilic and nucleophilic

atomic sites in molecules. Mathematically, the Fukui function (Eq. 1) is given as the first-order derivative of the electron density ($\rho(r)$) about the number of electrons (N) in the system at a constant external potential ($v(r)$) (WANG *et al.*, 2019).

$$f(r) = \left[\frac{\partial \rho(r)}{\partial N} \right]_{v(r)} \quad (1)$$

$$f_A^+ = q_N^A - q_{N+1}^A \quad (2)$$

$$f_A^- = q_{N-1}^A - q_N^A \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta f_A = f_A^+ - f_A^- \quad (4)$$

Condensed Fukui functions make it possible to carry out a quantitative analysis of the susceptibility of atomic sites. To calculate these functions, the atomic population number is used to represent the amount of electron density distribution around an atom. In this way, by applying the finite distance method, we can separately study the susceptibility of compounds to nucleophilic attack (f_A^+) (eq. 2) and electrophilic attack (f_A^-) (eq. 3). The condensed dual Fukui descriptor allows the susceptibility to nucleophilic and electrophilic attack to be studied simultaneously and is calculated from (eq. 4). For this work, the Hirshfeld population was chosen because it performs very well in the calculation of condensed Fukui functions (WANG *et al.*, 2019).

3. THEORETICAL REFERENCE

STLs are a group of molecules commonly found in plants of the Asteraceae family. These compounds have biological, allelopathic, insecticidal, and antimicrobial activities, and are also used as chemotherapeutic agents (BOGDANOVIĆ *et al.*, 2019).

As part of the guaianolide-type STLs, lactucin, and its derivative lactucopicrin are characterized by having a three-cycle structure and being extremely oxygenated (ÁVILA-GÁLVEZ *et al.*, 2023). Their conformations can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 2 – Optimized three-dimensional structures of Lactucin (A) and Lactucopicrin (B)

Source: Author (2023).

Fukui Condensed Functions offer an approach to predicting and understanding the chemical reactivity of molecules. These functions help to identify which atoms in a molecule are more likely to gain or lose electrons in chemical reactions. The f_A^+ function is useful for predicting where regions susceptible to nucleophilic attack will occur in a molecule, while the f_A^- function is useful for predicting where regions susceptible to electrophilic attack will occur (ASHBURN, 2019).

The condensed Fukui dual descriptor (Δf_A) makes it possible to study the susceptibility of electrophilic and nucleophilic sites simultaneously, where for $\Delta f_A > 0$ the site is favorable for a nucleophilic attack and for $\Delta f_A < 0$ the site is favorable for an electrophilic attack (RADDER *et al.*, 2022).

Table 1. Hirshfield charges and condensed Fukui functions for Lactucin

ATOM	$N - 1$	N	$N + 1$	f_A^+	f_A^-	Δf_A
C1	0,00417	-0,02795	-0,04735	0,01940	0,03212	-0,01272
C2	-0,00483	-0,01894	-0,02646	0,00752	0,01411	-0,00659
C3	0,071661	0,026315	-0,0334	0,05972	0,04535	0,01437
C4	-0,02415	-0,05849	-0,09421	0,03573	0,03434	0,00139
C5	0,182325	0,130552	0,055807	0,07474	0,05177	0,02297
O6	-0,03588	-0,26282	-0,36424	0,10142	0,22693	-0,12551
7C	0,079013	0,036049	-0,02239	0,05844	0,04296	0,01548
C8	-0,03621	-0,05283	-0,06548	0,01265	0,01662	-0,00396
C9	0,072149	0,063506	0,057855	0,00565	0,00864	-0,00299
C10	-0,0194	-0,02346	-0,02943	0,00596	0,00406	0,00190
C11	0,064907	0,061712	0,058392	0,00332	0,00319	0,00013
C12	-0,05991	-0,08514	-0,10188	0,01674	0,02523	-0,00849

C13	0,00147	-0,01372	-0,04159	0,02787	0,01519	0,01268
C14	0,208428	0,195887	0,162576	0,03331	0,01254	0,02077
O15	-0,11396	-0,12039	-0,1345	0,01411	0,00643	0,00767
C16	0,001886	-0,04297	-0,12243	0,07946	0,04485	0,03461
O17	-0,22059	-0,27121	-0,32893	0,05772	0,05063	0,00709
C18	0,04643	0,02895	0,013528	0,01542	0,01748	-0,00206
O19	-0,20234	-0,22507	-0,24426	0,01919	0,02273	-0,00354
H20	0,173877	0,160096	0,146552	0,01354	0,01378	-0,00024
H21	0,060723	0,043682	0,011635	0,03205	0,01704	0,01501
H22	0,074477	0,052649	0,017473	0,03518	0,02183	0,01335
H23	0,036694	0,027596	0,018468	0,00913	0,00910	0,00003
H24	0,057029	0,038613	0,01202	0,02659	0,01842	0,00818
H25	0,047198	0,033988	0,02205	0,01194	0,01321	-0,00127
H26	0,068068	0,03908	0,010542	0,02854	0,02899	-0,00045
H27	0,065702	0,03599	0,01036	0,02563	0,02971	-0,00408
H28	0,079674	0,050913	0,022614	0,02830	0,02876	-0,00046
H29	0,062845	0,039097	0,020178	0,01892	0,02375	-0,00483
H30	0,037536	0,031706	0,022994	0,00871	0,00583	0,00288
H31	0,048457	0,039318	0,019308	0,02001	0,00914	0,01087
H32	0,055069	0,035508	0,017714	0,01779	0,01956	-0,00177
H33	0,07033	0,04797	0,020897	0,02707	0,02236	0,00471
H34	0,051983	0,033372	0,014495	0,01888	0,01861	0,00027
O35	-0,17937	-0,20714	-0,2196	0,01247	0,02777	-0,01530
H36	0,174538	0,157575	0,140705	0,01687	0,01696	-0,00009

Source: Author (2023).

Table 2. Hirshfield charges and condensed Fukui functions for Lactucopicrin

ATOM	$N - 1$	N	$N + 1$	f_A^+	f_A^-	Δf_A
1 (C)	-0,01449	-0,02704	-0,04757	0,02053	0,01255	0,00797
2 (C)	-0,01183	-0,01894	-0,02621	0,00727	0,00711	0,00016
3 (C)	0,05311	0,02683	-0,03031	0,05714	0,02628	0,03086
4 (C)	-0,03804	-0,05767	-0,09061	0,03294	0,01964	0,01330
5 (C)	0,16214	0,13122	0,05859	0,07263	0,03092	0,04170
6 (O)	-0,13826	-0,26095	-0,35885	0,09790	0,12269	-0,02479
7 (C)	0,04961	0,03486	-0,02377	0,05863	0,01475	0,04389
8 (C)	-0,04409	-0,05085	-0,06275	0,01189	0,00677	0,00512
9 (C)	0,07012	0,06931	0,06552	0,00379	0,00081	0,00298
10 (C)	-0,02224	-0,02306	-0,02879	0,00573	0,00083	0,00490
11 (C)	0,06329	0,06212	0,05913	0,00299	0,00117	0,00182
12 (C)	-0,07315	-0,08473	-0,10074	0,01600	0,01158	0,00442
13 (C)	-0,01421	-0,01489	-0,04210	0,02722	0,00067	0,02654
14 (C)	0,20060	0,19685	0,16524	0,03161	0,00375	0,02786
15 (O)	-0,11482	-0,11894	-0,13215	0,01321	0,00412	0,00910
16 (C)	-0,03402	-0,03800	-0,11102	0,07302	0,00398	0,06905

17 (O)	-0,24583	-0,26840	-0,32285	0,05446	0,02257	0,03189
18 (C)	0,03925	0,02933	0,01473	0,01460	0,00992	0,00468
19 (O)	-0,21037	-0,22409	-0,24233	0,01823	0,01372	0,00451
20 (H)	0,16868	0,16065	0,14770	0,01295	0,00803	0,00492
21 (H)	0,04558	0,04606	0,01865	0,02741	-0,00048	0,02789
22 (H)	0,06270	0,05441	0,02338	0,03104	0,00828	0,02275
23 (H)	0,02711	0,03085	0,02594	0,00491	-0,00374	0,00864
24 (H)	0,05502	0,04238	0,01940	0,02298	0,01264	0,01034
25 (H)	0,04285	0,03465	0,02356	0,01109	0,00820	0,00289
26 (H)	0,05745	0,04097	0,01416	0,02681	0,01648	0,01032
27 (H)	0,04228	0,03429	0,00963	0,02466	0,00799	0,01667
28 (H)	0,06921	0,05171	0,02501	0,02670	0,01751	0,00919
29 (H)	0,05243	0,03972	0,02236	0,01737	0,01270	0,00466
30 (H)	0,03147	0,03252	0,02444	0,00808	-0,00105	0,00913
31 (H)	0,04849	0,04088	0,02311	0,01777	0,00761	0,01016
32 (H)	0,04673	0,03604	0,01887	0,01716	0,01069	0,00647
33 (H)	0,06193	0,04833	0,02337	0,02496	0,01360	0,01136
34 (H)	0,04270	0,03608	0,02024	0,01584	0,00662	0,00921
35 (O)	-0,10027	-0,11360	-0,11243	-0,00117	0,01333	-0,01449
36 (C)	0,21931	0,21258	0,20911	0,00347	0,00672	-0,00325
37 (O)	-0,23906	-0,27289	-0,29747	0,02458	0,03383	-0,00925
38 (C)	-0,03620	-0,04818	-0,04987	0,00169	0,01199	-0,01030
39 (C)	0,04825	-0,01085	-0,00624	-0,00460	0,05910	-0,06370
40 (C)	-0,00168	-0,03713	-0,03954	0,00241	0,03545	-0,03304
41 (C)	-0,01815	-0,06094	-0,07069	0,00975	0,04278	-0,03303
42 (C)	0,13222	0,07831	0,07062	0,00768	0,05391	-0,04622
43 (C)	-0,00632	-0,05265	-0,05833	0,00568	0,04633	-0,04065
44 (C)	-0,01310	-0,04067	-0,03869	-0,00198	0,02757	-0,02954
45 (O)	-0,11158	-0,18734	-0,19732	0,00998	0,07577	-0,06579
46 (H)	0,07331	0,05140	0,04140	0,01000	0,02191	-0,01191
47 (H)	0,04594	0,03766	0,04030	-0,00264	0,00827	-0,01091
48 (H)	0,06780	0,04532	0,04125	0,00407	0,02248	-0,01842
49 (H)	0,05862	0,04024	0,04266	-0,00242	0,01838	-0,02080
50 (H)	0,07571	0,05008	0,04446	0,00562	0,02564	-0,02002
51 (H)	0,06970	0,04297	0,03322	0,00975	0,02673	-0,01698
52 (H)	0,20410	0,17320	0,16458	0,00862	0,03090	-0,02228

Source: Author (2023).

Table 1 shows the values calculated for the condensed Fukui functions for Lactucin, where we can see that atoms C3, C4, C5, C7, C10, C11, C13, C14, C15, C16, O17, H21, H22, H23, H24, H30, H31, H33, and H34 present mainly in the B' and C' rings were susceptible to nucleophilic attack because they had $\Delta f_A > 0$, while the atoms C1, C2, O6, C8, C9, C12, C18, O19, H20, H25, H26,

H27, H28, H29, H32, O35 and 36H present mainly in the A' ring were susceptible to electrophilic attack as they had $\Delta f_A < 0$.

Table 2 shows the values calculated for the condensed Fukui functions for Lactucopicrin, where we can see that atoms C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, C7, C8, C9, C10, C11, C12, C13, C14, O15, C16, O17, C18, O19, H20, H21, H22, H23, H24, H25, H26, H27, H28, H29, H30, H31, H32, H33 and H34 present mainly in the A', B' and C' are susceptible to nucleophilic attack as they have $\Delta f_A > 0$, while atoms O6, O35, C36, O37, C38, C39, C40, C41, C42, C43, C44, O45, H46, H47, H48, H49, H50, H51 and H52, which are mainly in the acetaldehyde-substituted hydroxyphenyl group, have $\Delta f_A < 0$.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The molecular structures of Lactucin and Lactucopicrin were optimized using the Density Functional Theory formalism with the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory employed with energy values in the order of -26051.0816 eV and -38539.5861 eV respectively. Condensed Fukui functions were calculated to investigate the reactivity of atomic sites susceptible to nucleophilic and electrophilic attack. The atoms of the B' and C' rings of Lactucin proved to be more susceptible to nucleophilic attack, while the atoms of the A' ring proved to be more susceptible to electrophilic attack. For Lactucopicrin, the A', B', and C' ring atoms proved to be more susceptible to nucleophilic attack, while the acetaldehyde-substituted hydroxyphenyl group proved to be more susceptible to electrophilic attack.

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